

**THE CONDITION OF THE NASAL AND ORAL MUCOSA OF
MUCOCILIARY TRANSPORT, THE MAIN FUNCTIONS OF THE NOSE
AND MOUTH IN SMOKERS**

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Annotation: In any living organisms, the transfer of energy accompanies the physiological process. Energy means the ability to do a certain job. Thermodynamics as a science refers all living organisms to open systems, and one of the main conditions for their existence is a constant metabolism of substances and energy. All life processes are based on the reactions of atoms and molecules, which are carried out in accordance with the same fundamental laws that govern reactions outside the body. According to the first law of thermodynamics, energy never disappears and does not arise from nowhere, but all the time passes from one form to another.

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The metabolism of substances and energy refers to the totality of various physical, physiological and chemical processes of transformation of energy and substances in living organisms and the exchange of substances and energy between the body and the surrounding world. In living organisms, metabolism consists of the intake of various substances from the outside, their transformation and use in various processes of vital activity, as well as in the release of the resulting decay products into the environment. All transformations of energy and substances occurring in the body can be combined under a common name - metabolism (metabolism). At the cellular level, these transformations are carried out through sequences of biochemical reactions, which are called metabolic pathways, and can include more than a thousand different reactions. These reactions occur in a strictly defined sequence and are controlled by a variety of chemical and genetic

mechanisms. Metabolism can be divided into two interrelated, but at the same time multidirectional processes: anabolism (assimilation) and catabolism (dissimilation). Anabolism is a combination of various processes of biosynthesis of organic substances (components of cells and other tissues and organ structures). It promotes growth, development, renewal of biological structures, as well as the process of energy accumulation. This process consists in the chemical transformation of molecules coming from food into other more complex biological molecules.

The final product of metabolism includes carbon dioxide, water, carbon monoxide, urea, as well as other substances that contain nitrogen. Catabolism extracts chemical energy contained in food molecules and uses this energy to ensure the necessary functions of the body. In the organisms of higher animals, energy is synthesized using complex biochemical reactions, the main part of which is oxidation processes. Carbohydrates are the main substrate that undergoes oxidation. The share of carbohydrates as a substrate for energy production among other substances is more than 80%. Amino acids and fatty acids are also involved in the oxidation process. Oxygen acts as the only oxidizer (aerobic glycolysis). With its lack, a more ancient mechanism of energy production is triggered — anaerobic glycolysis, the efficiency of which is 18 times less.

To carry out the process of respiration, as well as the delivery of oxygen to each organ and cell of the body, a whole complex of structures has emerged in the form of organs of aeration, hemodynamics, synthesis of liquid tissue - blood, microcirculation, carrying out the closest connection with all tissues and cells. The respiratory tract, as an integral part of the respiratory system, ensures the delivery of oxygen to the lungs and the removal of carbon dioxide from it. During the breathing process, humidification, purification, warming of the inhaled air occurs, as well as the reception (perception) of olfactory, temperature and mechanical stimuli. From which it can be concluded that the main function of the respiratory tract is not just the movement of the gas mixture, but also adequate air preparation

for the most efficient gas exchange. At the same time, at the level of the respiratory tract, there is constant contact of the body with aggressive environmental factors.

The mucous membrane of the upper respiratory tract is one of the main protective barriers. Under the influence of microbial products and cytokines, the cells of the nasal mucosa secrete adhesion molecules, cytokines, which are important for the implementation of immune processes. The mucous membrane of the airways also has local immunity - MALT (Mucosal Associated Lymphoid Tissues). Lymphocytes that have been activated in the lymphoid tissue of the mucous membranes move to the regional lymph nodes and return to the mucous membranes through the thoracic duct and the bloodstream back. The complement system, mononuclear phagocytes, interferon and lysozyme, whose concentration in the tonsils is 300 times higher than in the blood serum, are also actively involved in the formation of local immunity. In the general system of immune competent organs, the lympho epithelial complex takes an active part in the formation of local and systemic immunity, which produces antibodies, forms immune memory cells, performs hematopoietic, informative, neuro reflective and protective functions.

Mucociliary transport is an extremely important mechanism for the rehabilitation of the respiratory tract, one of the main links of the local protection system, which provides the necessary potential for the barrier and immune function of the respiratory tract. The clearance of the respiratory tract from foreign microorganisms and particles occurs due to their settling on the mucous membranes and subsequent excretion together with mucus. When this mechanism is disrupted by an increase in the amount and thickening of mucus, as well as the formation of mucous plugs, bronchial obstruction increases, the risk of lung infection and bacterial colonization increases.

The general structure of the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses is characterized by a structured layered arrangement of its constituent elements. The standard is the surface epithelium on the basement membrane and its own connective tissue plate. Its own layer also contains mast

cells, tissue macrophages, basophils, eosinophils, plasma cells, neutrophils, fibrocytes, fibroblasts, histiocytes and dendritic cells, the number and ratio of which, depending on the stage of the inflammatory process, may vary.

The ciliated epithelium is covered with a secret consisting of two layers of periciliary fluid and the mucosal layer itself. The viscosity indices of the periciliary fluid have minimal values and, as a result, the movement of cilia in this medium does not meet much resistance. The mucus layer consists mainly of low- and high-density mucopolysaccharides, which are connected by transverse intermolecular bonds, the ratio of which determines the viscosity of the mucus. The total thickness of these two layers usually does not exceed 5-10 microns.

Approximately 60% of viable organisms linger on the surface of the nasal mucosa, however, the normal functioning of the mucociliary transport system reduces the risk that colonies will have time to grow from bacteria to a minimum.

In addition, the secret produced by the nasal mucosa contains biochemical protective specific and non-specific factors [24]. Non-specific factors include lysozyme, interferon, lactoferrin, glycoproteins (sulfomycins, fucomycins, sialomycins), complement (enzyme system), secretory proteases. Lysozyme has both bactericidal and bacteriostatic effects. The anti-bacterial action of lysozyme is due to its ability to destroy the glycosaminoglycans of the cell membrane of microbes, after which this cell becomes non-viable. Complement participates in immune reactions as a mediator and enhances them. Proteases regulate the functions of enzymes. Interferon has antiviral activity. It is a lymphokine, which, in turn, activates the phagocytic activity of macrophages and stimulates the formation of antibodies. The bactericidal effect of lactoferrin is manifested in its ability to bind iron, which is necessary for the vital activity of bacteria.

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